

Describe how the hydrology of river systems differ between Britain and southern Spain and discuss how this affects the flooding risks that they produce.

Rivers are paths for the natural movement of water from high to low topographies, and supply land-locked areas with fresh water that they would not otherwise find available. However, rivers can cause risks like flooding, which augment the nature of an ordinary river to a destructive force. Two types of rivers, perennial and ephemeral, can be observed in Britain and southern Spain respectively. In this essay I will describe how river systems of Britain and Spain differ in climate, rainfall, vegetation, soil, and geography, and how this affects their corresponding flood risks.

Perennial rivers, like those in Britain, are often seen in temperate climates, which experience high levels of consistent rainfall (Ward 2000). Also known as the process of throughflow; groundwater maintains water levels in rivers during droughts, and subsequently contributes to river overflow by “generating saturation-excess overland flow” (Holden, 2018, p.478). Thorne (2014) states that water tables of perennial systems in Britain generally take a week, to months of higher-than-average rainfall to reach full saturation, at which point flooding becomes a risk. Vegetation also plays a role in the hydrology of rivers via its effect on soil structure. Elwell and Stocking (1976) have shown that canopy cover, which intercepts raindrops before they reach soil, causes less disruption to soil structure due to the interruption of force. This disruption of energy allows the commonly clay soils of perennial rivers to remain porous and permeable, while absorbing water through the plate-like particles via capillary action (Ward 2000). Holden (2018, p.479) describes this effect as ‘soil water tension’, and further explains how soils with smaller pores (clay) exhibit this more often than those with larger pores (sand). Lastly, the soils of Britain make up its geography of low slope angles, which decrease rates of erosion and associated sediment transport due to gravity’s decreased effect (Parsons and Abrahams 2009). Perennial rivers of Britain’s low gradient slopes are affected by the preexisting climate and subsequent rainfall, which percolates through the water table. The soils of such water tables have high infiltration rates due to the vegetation surrounding the river catchment.

Fryirs and Brierley (2012, p.54) describe ephemeral rivers as “dry most of the year but may have seasonal flow”. Though seasonal, Fryirs and Brierley (2012) further illustrate how upon reaching ‘stage height’ or max capacity, an ephemeral river will overflow in a matter of hours, or even minutes, depending on the rainfall intensity and duration. Holden (2018) further explains how these rivers are often located in semi-arid areas, such as southern

Spain, where intense rainfall events and sparse vegetation cause impermeable soil crusts to develop. Consequently, the lack of vegetation in these climates allows for raindrop impact to cause rapid soil crusting (Ward 2000). Woodward (2009, p.237) even suggests that vegetation cover effectively “transforms the runoff regimes of Mediterranean catchments”. Ward (2000) also indicates how low infiltration capacity leaves these soils so dry that they become virtually hydrophobic. The Horton hypothesis, through flood analysis, demonstrates that a soil will absorb precipitation, limited only by infiltration capacity of the soil surface (Horton 1933). In the case of southern Spain soil is often crusted and has low infiltration capacity, therefore allowing the remaining but majority of unabsorbed rainfall to begin runoff and erosion processes. Southern Spain exhibits high slope gradients and, due to the increased force of gravity caused by this, more water moves over these areas with more speed than on a smaller slope angle (Holden 2018). Due to their seasonality of climate and rainfall, as well as scarce vegetation, ephemeral rivers have a very different soil profile and river hydrology to that of perennial rivers.

For a climate so familiar with water, such as humidity making a temperate climate, extreme flooding of perennial rivers in Britain is uncommon (Thorne 2014). Consequently, when a perennial river floods, it is due to the complete saturation of subsurface water, causing the entire water table to rise onto the floodplain (Fryirs and Brierley 2012). Fryirs and Brierley (2012) additionally point out that in this process, also known as saturation-excess overland flow, water will flow from high to low potential energy until it reaches the water table. At most times the water table is a somewhat flat layer at which the soil becomes

fully saturated with water. When this layer is above the ‘ground’, a river or pond forms, see figure 1, however this is also the point when flooding may occur.

Thorne (2014) describes the main 6

Figure 1: Water table graphic. Source: Holden

(2018) storms of winter 2013-14 in Britain, and how this combination of precipitation over December, January and February caused the historic flooding of the perennial Thames River. Only through the efforts of three months’ worth of rain, by 6 Atlantic depressions, was the ground able to become fully saturated and cause flooding. The high-water tolerance of perennial rivers allows for more preparation time before floods occur. Consequently, this same high-water tolerance causes resistance to any change in rainfall, with Thorne (2014) reporting some locations taking as long as a month to drain water from the floodplains.

Canopy cover however, as stated by Elwell and Stocking (1976), will not only increase the water tolerance of a river, allowing for more time for evacuation in case of flooding, but will also decrease the likeliness of soil crusting, which is known to accelerate flooding risks. Therefore, canopy cover indirectly decreases damage to soil structure, while vegetation directly strengthens the ground leaving it protected against run-off processes during floods. Holden (2018) notes how the lack of crusting indicates that the soil remains permeable, and the water table will take longer to fill-up, causing flooding to be less likely and more predictable. The low slope angles of Britain favour less intense overland flow of water during flood events, due to the diffused effects of gravity over the slow land gradients (Parsons and Abrahams 2009). The reduced intensity of excess-saturation water flow, over land during floods, will have less energy and subsequently less destructive power, reducing the general risk of perennial floods. Overall, the presence of vegetation in combination with climate including rainfall, and low slope gradients, causes a high infiltration rate in soil, and less intense flowing water, thereby decreasing flood risk.

Flood risk in ephemeral rivers too, is relatively uncommon, though for different reasons. Spain's arid climate and infrequent rainfall have a significant impact on its rivers by controlling their seasonality, as seen in Holden (2018). This prevailing lack of precipitation produces a very water intolerant soil profile, which can be observed in the timespan between rainfall and flooding. Woodward (2009, pp. 520-523) reports multiple instances of flooding in Spain during the 1900s, with one instance occurring in a valley, which subsequently flooded and of the 269 mm of rainfall in 24 hours, 226 mm took place over 3 hours. The main issue with ephemeral river flooding is that due to the low water capacity of the soil, flooding will begin faster upon the arrival of rainfall, which leaves very little time for preparation or evacuation. The lack of water sequestration in Spain is additionally due to lack of vegetation, which also contributes to damage of soil structure, in the form of soil crusting (Ward 2000). The Horton hypothesis indicates that the lack of soil permeability leaves rainfall very limited ways to escape, leading much of it to follow gravity down the steep slopes of southern Spain (Horton 1933). This process starts surface water run-off. Ward (2000) explains that the run-off will subsequently cause erosion, moving sediments and channelling deeper into the ground at higher slope gradients to reach the bottom at the most efficient rate possible. However, this faster rate of movement, due to gravity, causes more energy to be developed by the system, which in turn causes quicker floods with less warning, and stronger floods with more risk (Woodward 2009). The movement of sediment is important to flooding because it shows how much power the flood has to transport soil. Bull (1979) introduces how

this is measured in stream versus critical power. Stream power is defined as the power available in a river to move sediment, whereas critical power is the power needed to move the current sediment amount (Bull 1979). When these powers are balanced the system works effectively, but topography can favour one power or the other. The tectonic systems in southern Spain allow for stream power to be favoured in ephemeral rivers, making the potential for sediment movement grow during its flowing seasons and near nil outside of seasonal flows. This strong movement of sediment by water during ephemeral river flooding, is caused by low soil saturation by lack of vegetation, consequently due to climate and rainfall conditions of southern Spain.

British perennial and Spanish ephemeral rivers exist as opposites of each other in all categories of climate, rainfall, vegetation, soil and topography. Despite their different systems and associated floodings, both rivers provide their respective localities with necessary water.

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